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Project Newsletter

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Empowering Retail with AI

The INAIR project has reached an exciting milestone: the launch of its Open Educational Resources (OERs), a complete suite of multilingual and interactive learning materials designed to make Artificial Intelligence education accessible to retail MSMEs across Europe.

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OERs Validation and What's next?

Following validation with over 50 stakeholders across Europe, the OERs will soon be integrated into the INAIR e-learning environment. This next step will enable personalised learning paths, helping every retailer turn AI knowledge into actionable skills.

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Stay Tuned

Join the revolution! The AI revolution is here, and MSMEs have a unique opportunity to be at the forefront of this transformation.

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BRINGING AI EDUCATION TO LIFE THROUGH OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES (WP5)

The INAIR project has entered a new milestone: **the development and validation of Open Educational Resources (OERs)** – a full set of multilingual and interactive learning modules that will make AI learning accessible to retail MSMEs across Europe.

The OERs transform the AI Core Curriculum into practical, modular learning units designed for self-paced or guided training.

Each OER corresponds to one of the 16 learning blocks of the curriculum and includes real retail case studies, interactive simulations, learning games, and self-assessment tasks

The resources are available in six languages: **English, German, Greek, Italian, Polish, and Romanian.**

What do the OERs include?

Each module follows a standardised learning structure that integrates:

- clear learning objectives,
- hands-on examples from real retail operations,
- interactive exercises and knowledge checks,
- reflection activities and further reading.

The OERs cover three learning levels (**Foundation, Intermediate, Advanced**) and span topics such as:

- Introduction to AI
- Machine Learning & NLP in Retail
- AI for Inventory & Operations Optimisation
- Trustworthy and Ethical AI
- AI-Powered Customer Engagement

OERs

VALIDATION COMPLETED

The OERs underwent an international validation process with **55 participants**, including retail owners, employees, trainers, chambers of commerce, and technology consultants

Feedback confirmed that the OERs are:

- clear and pedagogically robust,
- usable and relevant for retail SMEs, and
- aligned with real business needs

Participants highlighted the practical relevance, the interactivity and the strong applicability in real retail settings.

What comes next?

The OERs will be integrated into the INAIR e-learning environment, enabling personalised pathways based on the AI Skills Assessment Tool and ready for pilot testing.

Turning knowledge into practical AI learning – accessible to every retailer.

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Join the AI Revolution

The AI revolution is here, and MSMEs have a unique opportunity to be at the forefront of this transformation. While challenges remain, the potential benefits of AI adoption in the retail sector are immense. With the right skills and strategies in place, MSMEs can unlock new levels of efficiency, customer satisfaction, and competitiveness. **We encourage all stakeholders to get involved**, whether by participating in future co-creation workshops, sharing your AI success stories, or joining us in developing the AI Core Curriculum.

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